

Preparation and Antimicrobial Activity of 4-Aryl-3-(phenazon-4'-yl)sydnonimine Hydrochloride

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4-Aryl-3-(phenazon-4'-yl)sydnonimine hydrochloride have been prepared by the treatment of 4-(α -cyanobenzylamino)phenazone with nitrous acid and methanolic hydrochloric acid. The constitution was supported by ir spectra. The products were screened for antibacterial activity.

SYDNONIMINE hydrochlorides possess biological activities like antituberculostatic¹, anti-allergic, antipyretic², anti-inflammatory³, analgesic⁴ and anticancer⁵. 4-Aminophenazone derivative also possess wide therapeutic activities, viz. antipyretic⁶, analgesic⁷ and anti-inflammatory⁸. With a view to synthesise better therapeutic agents, we have synthesised 4-aryl-3-(phenazon-4'-yl)sydnonimine hydrochlorides (1) by the action of nitrous acid and methanolic hydrochloric acid on α -cyanobenzylaminophenazone which were obtained by condensing 4-aminoantipyrine with different aldehydes cyanohydrine. The constitution was supported by ir spectra⁹. The products were screened for antibacterial activity. The ir spectra (KBr) of 4-phenyl-3-(phenazon-4'-yl)sydnonimine hydrochloride showed bands at 1600 (=NH), 1690 (C=N) and 1540 cm^{-1} (C=C).

Experimental

4-(α -Cyanobenzylamino)phenazones: To benzaldehyde (0.01 mol, 1.06 g) dissolved in ethanol (95% ; 25 ml) was added potassium cyanide, (0.01 mol, 0.66 g) in water (5 ml) followed by glacial acetic acid (0.01 mol, 0.60 g). The contents were stirred and 4-aminophenazone (0.01 mol, 2.03 g) was added, and the reaction mixture kept at 25–30° for 24 h. The product 4-(α -cyanobenzylamino)-phenazone was isolated and crystallised from ethanol (Found: C, 71.70; H, 5.06; N, 17.60. $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_4\text{O}$ required: C, 71.69; H, 5.66; N, 17.61%). Similarly, other aldehydecyanohydrines were condensed.

4-Phenyl-3-(phenazon-4'-yl)sydnonimine hydrochloride (1): The acetonitrile (0.01 mol, 3.16 g) was dissolved in concentrated hydrochloric acid (2 ml) and saturated solution of sodium nitrite (2 g in 4 ml water) added at 0°. After keeping the contents for 0.5 h, the nitroso compound was extracted with chloroform and dry hydrochloric acid was passed through it for 0.5 h in methanolic

solution and kept at 0–5° for 24 h. The solid product was filtered and crystallised from water (Found: C, 54.30; H, 5.00; N, 18.25. $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_5\text{O}$ required: C, 59.29; H, 4.98; N, 18.20%). Similarly, other compounds were prepared.

TABLE 1—4-(α -CYANOBENZYLAMINO)PHENAZONES

Sl. no.	R	Mol. formula*	M.p. °C	Yield %	Diameter of zone of inhibition (mm)**	
					<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>E. coli</i>
1.	Phenyl	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ N ₄ O	167	68	15	17
2.	<i>o</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ N ₄ O ₂	185	65	20	17
3.	<i>m</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ N ₄ O ₂	235	66	12	13
4.	<i>p</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ N ₄ O ₂	212	70	17	11
5.	3-Bromo-2-hydroxyphenyl	C ₁₅ H ₉ BrN ₄ O ₂	188	72	16	10
6.	3,5-Dibromo-2-hydroxyphenyl	C ₁₅ H ₇ Br ₂ N ₄ O ₂	169	79	14	18
7.	4-Hydroxy-3-methoxyphenyl	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₄ O ₃	110	80	13	11
8.	<i>p</i> -Dimethylaminophenyl	C ₁₇ H ₁₉ N ₅ O	142	82	14	09
9.	<i>m</i> -Nitrophenyl	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ N ₅ O ₂	198	58	17	12
10.	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ N ₅ O ₂	220	59	15	13
11.	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ N ₄ O ₂	162	62	17	12
12.	α -Furfuryl	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ N ₄ O ₃	115	60	14	11
13.	Cinnamyl	C ₂₁ H ₁₉ N ₄ O	99	64	13	18
14.	Isobutaryl	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ N ₄ O	147-48	65	14	10
15.	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ ClN ₄ O	120	61	16	13
16.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ ClN ₄ O	132	68	17	17

*All compounds gave correct nitrogen analysis. **In 24 h

TABLE 2—4-ARYL-3-(PHENAZON-4'-YL)SYDNONIMINE HYDROCHLORIDES

Sl. no.	R	Mol. formula*	Yield %	Diameter of zone of inhibition (mm)**	
				<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>E. coli</i>
1.	Phenyl	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ ClN ₅ O ₂	71	40	30
2.	<i>o</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	C ₁₉ H ₁₃ ClN ₅ O ₃	72	40	30
3.	<i>m</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	C ₁₉ H ₁₃ ClN ₅ O ₃	68	44	36
4.	<i>p</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	C ₁₉ H ₁₃ ClN ₅ O ₃	77	44	30
5.	3-Bromo 2-hydroxyphenyl	C ₁₉ H ₁₁ BrClN ₅ O ₃	79	40	30
6.	3,5-Dibromo 2-hydroxyphenyl	C ₁₉ H ₉ Br ₂ ClN ₅ O ₃	81	38	28
7.	4-Hydroxy-3-methoxyphenyl	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ ClN ₅ O ₄	78	40	22
8.	<i>p</i> -Dimethylaminophenyl	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ ClN ₆ O ₂	75	44	30
9.	<i>m</i> -Nitrophenyl	C ₁₉ H ₁₃ ClN ₆ O ₃	65	44	30
10.	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	C ₁₉ H ₁₃ ClN ₆ O ₃	68	44	30
11.	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ ClN ₅ O ₂	60	44	30
12.	α -Furfuryl	C ₂₅ H ₁₇ ClN ₅ O ₃	59	40	30
13.	Cinnamyl	C ₂₅ H ₁₉ ClN ₅ O ₂	62	38	22
14.	Isobutaryl	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ ClN ₅ O ₂	66	40	28
15.	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	C ₁₉ H ₁₃ Cl ₂ N ₅ O ₂	61	44	30
16.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	C ₁₉ H ₁₃ Cl ₂ N ₅ O ₂	69	44	36

*All compounds gave correct nitrogen analysis, m.p. of all compounds > 360°. **In 24 h.

Antibacterial activity: The compounds were tested for antibacterial activity against *S. aureus* and *E. coli* using disc method¹⁰. In case of 4-(α -cyano-benzylamino)phenazone, all the compound were moderately active against *S. aureus* and *E. coli*, while for sydnonimine hydrochloride derivatives, all the compounds showed high activity against *S. aureus* and *E. coli*. The test solution contained 0.5 mg of the product.

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